

INVESTIGATIONS ON THE DYNAMICS OF MACHINING OF COMPOSITES

G.Santhanakrishnan R.Krishnamurthy S.K.Malhotra
FRP Research Centre, Indian Institute of Technology
Madras 600 036 INDIA.

ABSTRACT

The different polymeric composites are very similar in their forming process, but each differs in its behaviour during machining. Face turning trials on FRP cylindrical tubes wound with glass, carbon and Kevlar fibres in epoxy matrix have been carried out to generate data and to create a basis for understanding the dynamics of machining of composites. With reference to the cutting forces measured and from the point of view of specific cutting pressure, the cutting characteristics of various tools used and the influence of tool work material pair have been analysed systematically and reported in this paper.

Keywords: Machining of composites, Glass, Carbon, Kevlar

1. INTRODUCTION

With higher specific strength and modulus, and enhanced resistance to corrosion, impact and fatigue wear, FRP composites are finding many engineering applications; this include components of aircraft, automobiles and other transport systems. For achieving near-nett shape for functional requirements and to ensure correct geometry for joints, fibre reinforced plastics (FRP) composites have to be machined. Machining of composites pose problems such as load fluctuations, severe abrasion and thermally associated tool wear [1,2]. Attempts on non-traditional machining such as laser or plasma cutting have not yielded good results due to the differential thermal properties between the fibre and the matrix material [3]. Hence conventional metal cutting operations have been resorted to; however defects such as fibre pull out, delamination and debonding associated with such machining have to be controlled by proper selection of tool material, tool geometry and working parameters. By this, it is possible to minimise the cutting force/pressure and thereby to control the defect. This paper presents data on the performance of different tools based on the dynamics of cutting for three types of FRP composites.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

Machining trials have been carried out on three types of composites using different cutting tools in a precision, high speed VDF lathe. The experimental details and work piece details are presented in Table 1. As indicated in the table all the three types of composites which are widely used in practice, have been machined by both plain cemented carbide (P and K type) and TiC and TiN coated tools using the cutting conditions listed in Table 1. For assessing the machinability of FRP composites as well as to gauge the performance of different tools all the three components of the cutting force ie. main cutting force (F_z), feed force (F_x) and thrust force (F_y) have been monitored using a high precision Kistler type tool dynamometer. Using these cutting force parameters and effective chip sections, the specific cutting pressure for all conditions of machining was calculated.

Table 1 - Machining Conditions

- Machine						
VDF Lathe						
Spindle speed: 140 - 5600rpm (stepless regulated)						
Motor power: 20Kw						
- Work Materials						
GFRP	-	Tubular section	132.0 mm OD	91.0 mm ID.		
CFRP	-	"	120.0 mm OD	97.5 mm ID.		
KFRP	-	"	122.6 mm OD	102.0 mm ID.		
Resin	-	Epoxy	Ciba Geigy LY556			
		Hardener	Ciba Geigy HT772			
Fibres	-	E-glass Roving,	Epoxy compatible - 2240Tex.			
		Carbon Roving,	BESFIGHT 6.4 μ filament dia			
			6000fibres/tow.			
		Kevlar-49 Roving	- 4560 DENIER-969, 546+16Tex.			
- Tool Material						
			γ	α	λ	κ
Carbides			-6	6	-6	75
(P30, K20)						90
Coated Carbides			-6	6	-6	75
(TiN/TiC coated)						90
- Cutting conditions						
Right hand turning						
Cutting speed:	V	m/min.	12.5 to 200			
Feed rate:	s	mm/rev.	0.025 to 0.15			
Depth of cut:	a	mm	1.5			
- Environment						
- dry						

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Dynamics of machining concerns with the study of machining forces and consequent influences. During machining of FRP composites, the cutting tool will encounter the forces in different directions depending upon the fibre orientations as schematically shown in Fig.1. This will result in oscillation of tool tip, resulting in non-steady cutting associated with plowing, low cycle fatigue of tool material and sometimes chipping of cutting edge of the tool. Apart from tool tip oscillation, the cutting tool also experiences higher order cutting temperature owing to poor thermal conductivity of composites. Thus during cutting, a cutting tool

Fig.1 Typical orientations of fibres encountered by the cutting tool during FRP machining

will experience a specific cutting pressure which is largely dependent on the type of composites being machined. This will decide the cutting force as presented in the following sections.

3.1 Machining of GFRP Composites

Fig.2 presents typical observation of cutting force experienced by the cutting tools during machining of GFRP composites. It is seen that for both P30 and K20 type tools, the cutting force increases with cutting velocity. During machining the cutting tool experiences an order of cutting temperature, depending upon the strain rate and work-tool material combination.

Generally the cutting temperature θ_c is given as

$$\theta_c = K_i (V)^b$$

- K_i - a constant
- V - cutting speed
- b - material dependent exponent

Thus, with increasing cutting velocity, the cutting tool will experience higher order temperature, which can affect the form-stability of the cutting wedge and thereby increase the cutting force as seen in Fig.2. The form stability of the cutting tool largely depends on the thermal conductivity, diffusivity and hot hardness characteristics; this is reflected in the occurrence of critical velocity V_c for each tool as illustrated in Fig.2. Temperature measurement during machining of FRP composites (Fig.3) reported by Sakuma [4] has also illustrated the occurrence of such a critical velocity. Coated carbides however exhibited a different trend. With lower velocity the tool experience the higher

Fig.2 Typical cutting force characteristics during GFRP machining

order cutting force due to plowing associated with the deformation of the coating; with increasing velocity the tools exhibited stable/steady cutting upto the critical velocity of 150 m/min, beyond which the cutting force registers an increasing trend. The performance of coated tools depend on thermal conductivity and hot hardness of the coating material. It is seen that while TiC coated tool exhibits lower cutting force with smaller feed values, it exhibited higher order forces with larger feed. This can be attributed to the hot hardness characteristics. Fig.4 presents a typical variation of hardness with temperature [5] for both TiC and TiN. The drop in hardness of TiC with higher temperature has resulted in increased cutting force with higher cutting feed. When machining with velocity greater than 150m/min. the TiN coating exhibited chipping over the cutting edges registering an increase in the cutting force.

3.2 CFRP Machining

Machining of carbon fibre reinforced plastics (CFRP) composites mostly involves perfect shearing/rupturing of carbon fibre, with very little deformation. The relatively harder CFRP composites when machined with lower velocity, can result in the cutting tool predominantly plowing on to the work surface; this leads to

Fig. 3 Relation between spindle speed & temperature at cutting edge [4]

Fig. 4 Temperature dependence of hardness of carbide and nitride [5]

higher order cutting forces with smaller cutting velocity as illustrated in Fig.5, which presents a typical variation of cutting force experienced during machining of CFRP composites. It is seen that all the cutting tools have exhibited a similar trend with critical velocity of 100m/min. The rapid rise in the cutting force for P30 tools while cutting under velocities greater than 100m/min. can be attributed to its hot hardness characteristics. At higher speeds the cutting tool experienced abrasion wear of the flanks, resulting in higher order cutting forces.

Referring to the Fig.5 it can be seen that the type of substrate can also influence the cutting force. Tools coated with TiC on two different substrates K and M types have been tried out for machining CFRP composites. While the K type substrate is known for its shock resistance, the M type is known for its toughness and hardness. It is seen that TiC coated over M type substrate exhibited a minimum variation in cutting force.

3.3 KFRP Machining

Unlike the GFRP and CFRP, Kevlar fibre reinforced plastics (KFRP) composites finds applications demanding higher hoop strength. The Kevlar fibre possesses enormous toughness compared to glass and carbon fibres as illustrated in Fig.6. The tenacious nature of Kevlar fibre posed considerable problems in machining, in that the lumps of fussy Kevlar fibres were often found to wrap around the cutting edge of the tool resulting in chipping of the same. In Fig 7. it is seen that P30 tools cut KFRP composites with minimum variation in cutting force while both K20 and coated carbides exhibited higher order forces. During machining it was observed fussy lumps of Kevlar coiled around the cutting tip resulted in cracking and chipping of the tool material over the cutting edge. This has caused rubbing over work piece, thereby minimum variation in cutting force for P30 tools. Both K20 and coated carbides cut KFRP with increased cutting force. Hence it is seen that for machining KFRP one has to minimise the formation of fussy lumps of Kevlar. This calls for a hard cutting tool with adequate fracture toughness and a sharp cutting nose.

Fig.5 Typical cutting force characteristics during CFRP machining

Fig. 6 Tensile and bending stress-strain characteristics of reinforcing fibres [6]

Fig. 7 Typical cutting force characteristics during KFRP machining

3.4 Observations on Specific Cutting Pressure

For evaluating the performance of cutting tool as well as the machinability of work material it is usual to refer to the specific cutting pressure experienced at the tool-work interface. The process of metal cutting in turning can be identified with indentation process in which the cutting tool indents on the work surface; in turning, the material removal is associated with plastic deformation and shearing of work material. Depending upon the bending characteristics, work material will resist the deformation and accordingly influence the specific pressures. Referring to Fig.6 it is seen that while carbon experiences rupture failure, Kevlar experiences more bending strain. This has resulted in minimum specific cutting pressure for CFRP and maximum for KFRP as seen in Fig.8. which shows typical variation of specific cutting pressure with cutting velocity for different tool-work material combinations. It is seen that depending upon the material pair, there exists a critical velocity of 100-150m/min. around which the specific cutting pressure is minimum. Compared to the plain carbides, the coated carbides experienced higher order pressure making them not so much suited for machining composites.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Based on the study on dynamics of machining of FRP composites, the following conclusions are drawn:

- The cutting tools experienced plowing force while cutting CFRP composites, with cutting velocity smaller than critical velocity, while with GFRP there is a rapid increase in cutting force with

Fig.8 Influence of tool -work material pair on specific cutting pressure

cutting velocity. This can be attributed to possible thermal effects associated with GFRP composites.

- Occurrence of fussy lumps of kevlar chip posed considerable problem such as chipping, which has resulted in higher order cutting force.

- Among the composites higher order brittleness of carbon fibre caused perfect rupturing of fibre, resulting in lower order specific cutting pressure for CFRP composites.

5. REFERENCES

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